

Mn²⁺ Catalysed Oxidation of Isopropyl Alcohol by Ce⁴⁺ in H₂SO₄ Medium

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Manuscript received 8 September 1971; revised 7 December 1972; accepted 5 February 1973

The rate of oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by Ce⁴⁺ in sulphuric acid medium increases with increases in Mn²⁺ concentration. Kinetic study suggests that Mn³⁺ might be the reactive species and that Mn³⁺ oxidises the alcohol via a 1 : 1 complex. The thermodynamic parameters for the reaction in the presence and absence of Mn²⁺ are also given.

Ce⁴⁺ is known to react with Mn²⁺ by the reaction

$$\text{Ce}^{4+} + \text{Mn}^{2+} \xrightarrow{\text{fast}} \text{Mn}^{3+} + \text{Ce}^{3+} \quad (1),$$
Mn³⁺ being unstable undergoes auto-oxidation and reduction by the reaction¹.

$$2\text{Mn}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Mn}^{2+} + \text{Mn}^{4+} \quad (2).$$
In most cases Mn⁴⁺ gets precipitated as MnO₂ unless either the acid concentration is kept high (~2.5 M) or excess Mn²⁺ is used. Under the above conditions the species which oxidises the substrate could be either Ce⁴⁺, Mn³⁺ or Mn⁴⁺.

In the absence of Mn²⁺ at constant [H⁺] the rate equation obtained for the oxidation of isopropanol by Ce⁴⁺ was

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} = k''[\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{alcohol}].$$

In the presence of Mn²⁺ the rate

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{d[\text{ketone}]}{dt}$$

increased with increase in [Mn²⁺] reaching a limiting value at high [Mn²⁺].

The order of [alcohol] changed from one (in the absence of Mn²⁺) to 0.75 (in the presence of Mn²⁺) indicating the possibility of alcohol being involved in complex formation with any of the oxidising species viz., Ce⁴⁺, Mn³⁺ or Mn⁴⁺. Since Ce⁴⁺ does not form a complex with alcohol in H₂SO₄ medium² the possibility is with either Mn³⁺ or Mn⁴⁺. Under conditions of [Mn²⁺] ≫ [Ce⁴⁺] one might expect all Ce⁴⁺ to be utilised in reaction (1); and due to the shifting of equilibrium (2), the oxidising species available should be Mn³⁺.

Banerji, Nath and Bakore³ have reported that the ΔE value, for the oxidation of acetone by Mn³⁺ sulphate in the presence of large excess of Mn²⁺, was about 23.0 Kcals. Under the same conditions using Ce⁴⁺ instead of Mn³⁺ sulphate we get a value of 22.9 Kcals for ΔE±, suggesting that Mn³⁺ is the oxidising species under our conditions also. In the oxidation of isopropanol by Ce⁴⁺ (5 × 10⁻³ M and [H₂SO₄] = 2.5 M) the ΔE± changes from 25.5 Kcals (in the absence of Mn²⁺) to 30.8 Kcals (in the presence

of excess Mn²⁺ = 0.22 M) supporting our contention that the oxidising species is probably Mn³⁺ and not Ce⁴⁺. Also it is clear from the fractional order of alcohol (Table 1) that the mechanism of oxidation is via 1 : 1 complex between Mn³⁺ and alcohol.

From the above mechanism the rate equation comes out to be

$$\frac{-d \ln [\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{alcohol}]}{1 + K[\text{alcohol}]}$$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [ISOPROPANOL] ON THE OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS

[Ce⁴⁺] = 5 × 10⁻³ M; [H⁺] = 2.5 M; [Mn²⁺] = 2.2 × 10⁻¹, T = 51.5°

[ROH] Moles lit ⁻¹	k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	log [ROH] + 1	log k' + 3
0.8	2.5	0.9031	0.3979
1.3	3.7	1.1139	0.5682
1.6	4.1	1.2041	0.6128
2.0	4.8	1.3010	0.6812
2.6	6.4	1.4150	0.8062
3.3	7.5	1.5185	0.8751
4.0	8.4	1.6021	0.9243

which accounts for the fractional order of alcohol. The thermodynamic parameters for the uncatalysed and catalysed (in brackets) are as follows :—

$$k' \times 10^7 \text{ at } 51.5^\circ = 3.6 \pm 0.1 (19.7 \pm 0.1) \text{ l.mol.}^{-1} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta E^\ddagger = 25.5 \text{ Kcals (30.8), } \Delta H^\ddagger = 24.2 \text{ Kcals mole}^{-1}$$

$$(29.5)$$

$$\Delta F^\ddagger = 30.8 \text{ Kcals mol}^{-1} (29.0), \Delta S^\ddagger = -20.3 \text{ eu}$$

$$(+1.5)$$

The experimental methods are same as in our earlier paper 2.

References

1. T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1181.
2. B. SETHURAM and S. S. MUHAMMAD, *Acta. Chim. Hung.*, 1965, 46, 112.
3. K. K. BANERJI, P. NATH and G. V. BAKORE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 337.